

**APPENDIX B - GUIDING QUESTIONS USED IN THE GROUP INTERVIEW
ABOUT MOBILE UX IMPROVEMENT**

Scale	Questions
Perceived Usefulness	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1.Is HTA useful for the evaluation process and suggestion of Mobile UX improvements within the Company?2.Will HTA optimize time in Mobile UX evaluation?3.How can the HTA diagram be useful in defining the user's journey when interacting with some task?
Perceived Ease	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1.Is HTA easy to apply in Mobile UX flow design?2.Are the HTA diagrams clear and objective to understand the steps taken by the user in the execution of a task?
Lessons Learned	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1.Do I intend to use HTA for Enterprise Mobile UX assessment?2.Based on the reality of the company, do I predict that I will use HTA in the Company?
Future Expectations	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1.In your view, what main lessons can be drawn from this moment?2.What is the main challenge in the UX improvement process and definition of user flows in the Company?3.What is your opinion when comparing the use of HTA with the procedure used previously in the Company to improve Mobile UX?